

Multi-service Single Tenant 5G Fronthaul Resource Orchestration Framework based on Network Slicing

Massimiliano Maule, John S. Vardakas, Georgios Kormentzas, and Christos Verikoukis

Abstract—With the evolution of 5G networks towards fully software, Network Slicing (NS) has emerged as a new paradigm to create a set of customised logical network instances on top of the same physical infrastructure. Telecom operators provide “slices” of their networks to different industries (e.g., automotive, Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), and eHealth), targeting to increase the resource utilization and Return on Investment (ROI). However, as the service demand increases, slice management becomes particularly complex, especially in the Radio Access Network (RAN) section, since virtualized infrastructures are significantly more complex to manage compared to physical networks. In this paper, a novel 5G New Radio (5G NR) NS management framework is presented, which targets to define the optimal NS parameterization for the entire Fronthaul (FH) 5G network. Our solution is divided into three phases: i) definition of the 5G Downlink Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (DL-HARQ) parameters (K0, K1), ii) the dynamic (inter-slice) partitioning of the radio resources among the slices, inline with the Service Level Agreement (SLA), and, iii) an intra-slice scheduling algorithm for the user prioritization, given real-time user’s traffic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) analysis. To the best of our knowledge, the proposed solution is the first attempt of a real-time NS management framework for the complete FH section, involving frame granularity service customization.

Index Terms—Network Slicing, 5G NR, HARQ timing, Functional Split, Game Theory, Network Design Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Network Slicing (NS) enables programmability and modularity in the provisioning of network resources with respect to specific vertical segment service requirements, thereby advancing the apriori 4G monolithic architecture. In particular, if combined with 5G Standalone (5G SA) Option 2 [1], NS adds full support to new 5G services, including enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), massive Machine-Type Communication (mMTC), and Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC), such that an operator is able to build and customize the End-to-End (E2E) infrastructure for different use cases/traffic types and to provide isolation between them [2].

The coexistence of the aforementioned 5G services is possible only through the shared usage of a common physical

infrastructure, spanning over different technical domains (e.g., Access Network (AN), Core Network (CN), and Transport Network (TN)) as well as administrative domains (e.g., referring to different mobile network operators). From a management perspective, the former one-size-fits-all techniques are unsuitable for the future 5G and beyond services ([3], [4], and [5]), since a central point of management is not compliant with the disaggregated 5G architecture and extreme demanding constraints, especially in the RAN part [6]. In [7], the authors present a RAN slice scheduling method based on utility function, capable of creating, executing and dismissing multiple services from the operator perspective. However, the exploitation of the Uplink (UL) control feedback information from each UE might have improved the RAN sharing policy, while reducing under/over resource provisioning.

For vertical industries, authors in [8] design a Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) RAN controller based on Reinforcement Learning (RL), where the resources are independently orchestrated among parallel multi-purpose services. Since the training phase might be extremely complex to model for fast varying scenarios, the proposed solution might not accomplish the high demanding 5G NR requirements for low latency applications. In [9], the authors focus on the integration of virtualized network services running at the edge, able to facilitate vehicular end-users and their respective systems. In the RAN, the project proposes a Slice Manager (SM) able to minimize the Round-Trip Time (RTT) through advanced Time Division Duplex (TDD) pattern and a reduced scheduling request period. Although the proposed method presents high RAN performance, the 5G frame format characteristics are not fully used, limiting the final performance.

The aforementioned state-of-the-art highlights the increased degree of flexibility and customization introduced with 5G technology. For this reason, Service Providers (SPs) require novel mechanisms where data transmission, processing, and storage are now merged together over a common infrastructure. In this light, this work presents a real-time NS orchestration framework specifically designed for the FH section, where the network resources and Network Functions (NFs) are customized per slice, following a cross checked analysis of the slice SLA and traffic’ KPIs per User Equipment (UE). The contributions and novelties of this paper are as follows:

- 1) *Phase 1*: for each slice, the optimal RAN NFs displacement is defined, given the service latency requirements and FH infrastructure capabilities. To support services with distinct requirements, given the single UE’s traffic characteristics, the optimal configuration of DL timing

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M. Maule is with Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain (e-mail:massimiliano.maule@upc.edu).

J. Vardakas is with Iquadrat Informatica S.L., Barcelona, Spain (e-mail:jvardakas@iquadrat.com).

G. Kormentzas is with University of the Aegean, Samos, Greece (e-mail:gkorm@aegean.gr).

C. Verikoukis is with University of Patras, Patras, Greece, ATHENA/ISI, Greece, and Iquadrat Informatica S.L., Barcelona, Spain (email:cveri@upatras.gr).

parameters (K0, K1) per UE are computed, together with the FH architecture delay requirements. As it will be illustrated in Subsection III-B, the proposed method performs Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) procedure up to four times faster than 4G, reducing the HARQ RTT through new flexible frame pattern schemes.

- 2) *Phase 2*: the framework computes the optimal radio resource sharing among the RAN slices such that the service data rate requirements are guaranteed under the SLA constraints [10]. The proposed solution maximizes the resource utilization factor per slice, such that resource sharing policies are guaranteed. Using as baseline the resource sharing schemes proposed in our previous work [11], the proposed inter-slice scheduling algorithm guarantees seamless service even under unexpected wireless channel variations. The performance of this method is discussed in Subsection III-C, in comparison with the static thresholds configuration.
- 3) *Phase 3*: a UE weight is calculated in order to define a scheduling priority within each slice according to each single UE latency and data rate requirements. The weight has the role to define the amount of radio resources per UE as a percentage of the total slice capacity, and it also defines the scheduler queue policy such that high demanding UEs are prioritized. While *Phase 2* is based on a Markov process, the UEs' weight distribution is modelled using the Socially Optimal Allocation (SOA) scheme [12]. The proposed SOA weight allocation scheme aims to maximize a network utility function, providing higher accuracy compared to the classical scheduling approaches, as presented in Subsection III-C.

Thus, in this paper, starting from the FH architecture constraints and requirements per service, a hierarchical management of the whole RAN NS life cycle is proposed, exploiting the latest parameterization capabilities standardized in 5G, such as scalable numerologies, variable Transmission Time Interval (TTI), distributed processing, and flexible timing.

II. MODEL DESIGN

We cast a classical NS scenario, where the Mobile Network Operator (MNO) controls the infrastructure resources inline with the tenants' SLAs. Hereafter, we describe our assumptions and mathematically formulate the problem, following the proposed 3-phases methodology.

A. Scenario Overview

Let S_n^j denote the slice $n \in (n = 1, \dots, N^j)$ in the system belonging to the tenant j , where N^j is the number of slices of the j -th tenant. Each slice S_n^j is characterized by an initial capacity C_n^j such that:

$$\sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{n=1}^{N^j} C_n^j = C_{rrh}^{cell} \quad (1)$$

where C_{rrh}^{cell} represents the total cell capacity of the Remote Radio Head (RRH) element rrh , where $rrh \in (1, \dots, R_{rrh})$, and R_{rrh} the total number of RRHs in the system. Each slice S_n^j is characterized by the following parameters:

$$[D_n^{j,harq}; \mathbf{R}_n^j; th_{n,1}^j, th_{n,2}^j; \mathbf{W}_n^j], 0 < th_{n,1}^j < th_{n,2}^j < 1 \quad (2)$$

where $D_n^{j,harq}$ is the vector of the RTT HARQ delay required for each UE served by the slice n of tenant j , \mathbf{R}_n^j is the vector of average required throughput for each UE served by the slice n of tenant j , $th_{n,1}^j$ is the percentage of radio resources assigned to the n -th slice of the j -th tenant in *Support* mode, $th_{n,2}^j$ is the percentage of radio resources assigned to the n -th slice of the j -th tenant in *Conservative* mode, and \mathbf{W}_n^j is the vector of UEs' weights of slice n of tenant j .

In this work, the mathematical formulation and experimental part are presented for a single tenant scenario ($j = 1$). For an exhaustive explanation of the following mathematical part, we refer to our previous work in [13], which analyses our FH orchestration framework in a multi-tenant scenario.

B. Phase 1: DL HARQ Timing Parameters

In Phase 1, the optimal set of DL HARQ timing parameters ($K0_{u,n}$, $K1_{u,n}$) and slice FP option D_n is determined, according to the latency requirement of each served UE and slice SLA. By varying the numerology, different maximum data-rate performance can be achieved for each slice. For this reason, the first optimization aims to select the combination of slices whose sum of maximum data rates do not exceed the cell capacity constraint C_{rrh}^{cell} :

$$\begin{aligned} Z &= C_{n,\mu} + C_{n+1,\mu} + \dots + C_{N_j,\mu} \leq C_{rrh}^{cell} \\ \forall n \in (1, \dots, N), \quad \forall \mu \in \mathbf{M}_n \\ I_{rrhK \times N} &= \begin{bmatrix} S_{1,\mu} & \dots & S_{N_j,\mu} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ S_{1,\mu} & \dots & S_{N_j,\mu+1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ S_{1,\mu+1} & \dots & S_{N_j,\mu} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$K = \left(\prod_{n \in N} \binom{|\mathbf{M}_n|}{1} \right) - |Z^c|$$

where \mathbf{M}_n represents the vector of numerologies μ , $C_{n,\mu}$ is the maximum achievable radio capacity of slice $S_{n,\mu}$, $I_{rrhK \times N}$ as the matrix where each row ($k \in K$) represents a set of slices combinations (without repetition) whose capacity $C_{n,\mu}$, and Z^c is the complement set of Z .

Inline with the 5G NR standard, different TTI values can be considered according to the type of scenario. For this reason, we propose the following three numerologies' cases:

- numerology 0 ($\mu = 0$, SCS = 15 KHz) and 1 ms TTI.
- numerology 1 ($\mu = 1$, SCS = 30 KHz) and 0.5 ms TTI.
- numerology 2 ($\mu = 2$, SCS = 60 KHz) and 0.25 ms TTI.

According to our investigation, these combinations represent a trade-off between the current state-of-the-art [14], and real 5G scenarios implementation at Frequency Range 1 (FR1) [15].

Table I: Infrastructure timing parameters

Parameter	Description	Parameter	Description
T_{air}	Air time	$T_{proc-rru}$	RRU processing time
$T_{prop-fh}$	FH propagation time	$T_{proc-du}$	DU processing time
$T_{prop-mh}$	MH propagation time	$T_{proc-cu}$	CU processing time
$T_{prop-bh}$	BH propagation time	T_{tx}	Transmission time
T_{rx}	Receiver time	$T_{proc-cn}$	CN processing time
D_{du}	RTT delay user-DU	D_{cu}	RTT delay user-CU
D_{cn}	RTT delay user-CN	TTI_n^j	TTI value of slice n in tenant j

Focusing on the DL direction, the DL HARQ RTT is measured from the time the UE receives the first DL-PDCCH, until the re-transmitted data are correctly decoded in the corresponding PDSCH subframe. For each solution $k \in I_{rrh}$, the parameters $K0_{u,n}$, $K1_{u,n}$ are determined for each UE $u \in U_n$ such that $(K1_{u,n} - K0_{u,n})$ is maximized, given the UE HARQ RTT ($D_{u,n}^{harq}$) and the architectural delay constraints. The resulting timing parameters' matrix $TM_{k \times E}$ is:

$$TM_{k \times E} = \max_{K0_{u,n}; K1_{u,n}} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{u=1}^{U_n} TTI_n \times ((K1_{u,n}) - (2 \times (\frac{\mu^{pdsch}}{\mu^{pdcch}} + K0_{u,n}))) + D_n$$

s.t.

$$0 < D_{du} < D_{cu} < D_{cn},$$

$$K0_{u,n} \in (0, 32), \quad K1_{u,n} \in (0, 15),$$

$$0 \leq K0_{u,n} < K1_{u,n},$$

$$TTI_n \times ((K1_{u,n}) - (2 \times K0_{u,n})) + D_n \leq D_{u,n}^{harq},$$

$$D_{u,n} = \begin{cases} (T_{air}^n + T_{prop-mh}^n + T_{prop-bh}^n) \times 2 + T_{rx}^n + T_{tx}^n + T_{proc}^n & \text{if } D_{cn} \leq D_{u,n}^{harq}, \\ (T_{air}^n + T_{prop-mh}^n) \times 2 + T_{rx}^n + T_{tx}^n + T_{proc}^n & \text{if } D_{cu} \leq D_{u,n}^{harq} < D_{cn}, \\ (T_{air}^n) \times 2 + T_{rx}^n + T_{tx}^n + T_{proc}^n & \text{if } D_{du} \leq D_{u,n}^{harq} < D_{cu}. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where K is defined in (3), $E = \sum_{n=1}^N |U_n|$ is the number of users served by each slice, $K0_{u,n}$ and $K1_{u,n}$ are the DL HARQ timing parameters of user u of slice n , TTI_n is the TTI value of slice n , $\frac{\mu^{pdsch}}{\mu^{pdcch}}$ is a correction numerology factor between control and data channels, and $D_{u,n}$ is the RTT infrastructure delay for user u ; these parameters are listed in Table I.

An important consideration is deduced from the structure of $TM_{K \times E}$: embedding all the N slices parameters in a single equation improves the stability of the FH infrastructure, since each $[K0_{u,n}, K1_{u,n}]$ pair is calculated taking into account the other slices settings. Through this cell-based unselfish approach, the nodes of FH infrastructure are always balanced and an higher NFs disaggregation can be considered per slice, unlike the limited configurations obtained with the classic manual/static FP assignment.

This subsection illustrated our innovative approach to determine the timing parameters of a flexible 5G frame structure, considering the HARQ latency requirements of a multi-slice scenario, and the E2E system architecture requirements.

C. Phase 2: inter-slice scheduler and thresholds optimization

After the completion of Phase 1, the proposed SM enables the inter-slice scheduler to perform in real-time the allocation of radio resources among the served slices, proportional to the slice's traffic load [16]. This method outperforms the ordinary RAN slicing approaches where the radio resources follow a static approach, without considering a real-time feedback from the UEs [17]. For each row $k \in I_{rrh}$, the radio bandwidth utilization for each slice $S_n \in k$ is expressed in PRBs, which can be approximated as:

$$PRB_n = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{u=1}^{U_n} \frac{r_{u,n} \times 10^3}{C_f \times \log_2(QAM_n) \times 2^\mu} \quad (5)$$

$$C_f = N_{n,sc} \times N_v^{cell} \times f^{cell} \times R_{n,code} \times 168 \times (1 - OH_n)$$

where $r_{u,n}$ is the data-rate (in Mbps) required by user u , QAM_n is the modulation order, μ the slice numerology, $N_{n,sc}$ the number of carriers, N_v^{cell} the number of layers, f^{cell} is a scaling factor, $R_{n,code}$ is the coding rate, and OH_n^j is the overhead factor. Once defined, the PRB_n parameter represents the real-time RB utilization index of the slice n in the $k - th$ row, and it is used to label the slice according to a specific resource sharing policy:

- *Support mode* ($0 < PRB_n \leq th_{n,1} \times C_n$): the slice accepts incoming service requests, and it can share radio resources with the other slices.
- *Conservative mode* ($th_{n,1} \times C_n < PRB_n \leq th_{n,2} \times C_n$): the slice prioritizes its own traffic by disabling sharing of radio resources with others.
- *Critical mode* ($th_{n,2} \times C_n < PRB_n \leq C_n$): the amount of allocated resources does not satisfy the SLA. If exists at least one slice in *Support mode*, resource sharing from the *Support* slice to the *Critical* slice can be performed.

As a further improvement to assist the resource sharing procedure, slice thresholds can be dynamically reconfigured, as illustrated in the following expression:

$$\max_{th_{n,1}} \frac{\lambda_n}{\sum_N \lambda_n} \sum_{u=th_{n,1} \cdot C_n}^{th_{n,2} \cdot C_n} P_n(u, C_n) \leq P_n \quad (6)$$

$$0 < th_{n,1} < th_{n,2} < 1$$

where $P_n(u, C_n)$ is the *slice blocking probability*, and P_n the maximum *cell blocking probability*. For each slice, (6) aims

Fig. 1. Initial slice resources partitioning.

to maximize $th_{n,1}$, such that the probability of one or more slices in *Support* mode is higher. The constraint on the *slice blocking probability* $P_n(i, C_n)$ guarantees that no slices violate their own SLA by exceeding the maximum *system blocking probability* P_n^j . An exhaustive mathematical explanation of the role of the *slice blocking probability* is provided in [11].

D. Phase 3: Intra-slice scheduler: user weight definition

In this subsection, an intra-slice scheduler is proposed, where a priority policy per UE is applied according to the traffic characteristics.

For each row $k \in I_{rrh}$, a weight $w_{u,n} \in \mathbf{W}_n$ is calculated for each UE u by maximizing the utility function $U(\mathbf{W}_n)$ according to the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \max(U(w_{1,1}, w_{2,1}, \dots)) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{u=1}^{U_n} \varphi_{u,n} \times f_q(w_{u,n}) \\ f_q(w_{u,n}) &= \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1-\alpha_q} \left(\frac{w_{u,n} \times PRB_{u,n}}{\sum_{u=1}^{U_n} w_{u,n}} \right)^{1-\alpha_q}, & \text{if } \alpha_q \neq 1 \\ \log\left(\frac{w_{u,n} \times PRB_{u,n}}{\sum_{u=1}^{U_n} w_{u,n}}\right), & \text{if } \alpha_q = 1 \end{cases} \quad (7) \\ \sum_{u=1}^{U_n} w_{u,n} &= C_n, \quad w_{u,n} > 0, \quad C_n > 0, \quad \alpha_q \geq 0, \\ PRB_{u,n} &= \frac{r_{u,n} \times 10^3}{C_f \times \log_2(QAM_n) \times 2^\mu}, \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{W}_n is the resulting UEs weight allocation vector, C_n is the radio capacity of slice S_n , $\varphi_{u,n}$ is the priority factor of UE u in slice S_n , and f_q the α_q utility function.

The proposed scheme belongs to the game-theory class entitled Self Organizing Allocation (SOA) [18], where the optimal allocation strategy is defined, and any other resource allocation scheme does not improve the performance. Moreover, in the experimental section, we perform our analysis for $\alpha_q = 1$, which corresponds to the proportional fairness criterion resource allocation.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK PERFORMANCE

A. Scenario overview

In this section, we validate the performance of our proposed algorithms via a comprehensive experimental procedure. The simulated scenario considers an E2E architecture with

Fig. 2. Final inter-slice resource optimization partitioning.

Fig. 3. User weight distribution using SOA.

three slices ($N = 3$), arranging different class of services ($S_1 = eMBB, S_2 = mMTC, S_3 = uRLLC$). For the scenario modelling, a 5G event-driven simulator based on Matlab R2019a [19] has been used, where the DL and UL transport channels have been modelled using the Matlab 5G-NR Toolbox. Moreover, each element of our topology is interconnected using fiber links, introducing a topology delay values as summarized in Table II.

The amount of radio resources and the number of UEs served per slice is selected such that the reader has a clear vision of the sharing capabilities of the proposed algorithms. For this reason, in the RAN section, the 5G gNB offers a bandwidth of 100 MHz (C_{rrh}^{cell}) at band n78 TDD in FR1, and the average number of UEs simultaneously served per slice depends on the type of service (3 eMBB, 8 mMTC, and 6 uRLLC), according to distinct Poisson distributions. Moreover, each service is shaped following the corresponding 3GPP specifications ([20], [21], [22]): for the eMBB slice, each UE receives an average data rate $r_{u,n} \in \mathcal{P}(20, 100)$ Mbps (3GPP TS 22.261), and an average UE latency constraint value $D_{u,n}^{harq} \in \mathcal{P}(8, 16)$ ms. For mMTC slice, the average user data rate is $r_{u,n} \in \mathcal{P}(5, 20)$ Mbps (3GPP TR 37.868), and average user latency constraint $D_{u,n}^{harq} \in \mathcal{P}(5, 10)$ ms. service HARQ RTT. For the uRLLC slice, an average of 6 users are connected simultaneously, with a data rate $\mathcal{P}(5, 40)$ Mbps (3GPP TR 23.725), and $\mathcal{P}(2, 4)$ ms. service HARQ RTT.

B. HARQ timing parameters definition

Assuming that each slice can choose among 3 numerologies ($M_n = [0, 1, 2], \forall n$), Fig. 5-top illustrates the K groups of slices, which total capacity satisfies (3). For a better un-

Table II: Infrastructure delay and radio parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
T_{air} (ms)	$\sim N(180,1) \times 3 \times 10^{-5}$	$T_{prop-fh}$ (ms)	$\sim P(4)$
$T_{prop-mh}$ (ms)	$\sim P(10)$	$T_{prop-bh}$ (ms)	$\sim P(20)$
T_{tx} (ms)	$\frac{1518 \times U_n^j }{\sum r_n^j} \times 10^3$	T_{rx} (ms)	$\frac{1518 \times U_n^j }{\sum r_n^j} \times 10^3$
T_{proc} (ms)	$\sim P(5)$	$C_1^{cell,1}$	100 MHz
$C_2^{cell,2}$	90 MHz	$C_3^{cell,3}$	100 MHz

Fig. 4. Jain index under increasing alpha value.

derstanding, let's consider, as an example, the 12-th row $I_{rrh_{12 \times 3}} = [S_{1,1}, S_{2,0}, S_{3,2}]$, where the maximum radio capacity per slice under the given traffic load is: $C_{1,1} = 39 MHz$, $C_{2,0} = 10 MHz$, and $C_{3,2} = 39 MHz$. Since $Z = 88 MHz$ satisfies the upper-bound cell condition of $100 MHz$, this combinations of slice-numerology is a valid candidate for our system. Through this first refinement, $K = 22$ combinations of the 3 slices are accepted, whose maximum performance is guaranteed even under fully resource utilization cases.

Fig. 5-bottom represents the Gaussian distribution of $K0_n$ and $K1_n$ for each slice, and averaged among the K valid combinations. For eMBB traffic, our model estimates that $K1 = 10$, allowing the deployment of all the RAN NFs for eMBB traffic in the CN. As the latency constraints become more stringent, the timing parameters slot interval is reduced. In our simulation, this is the case of the uRLLC slice, where the average gap between $K1_n$ and $K0_n$ is 4 slots. For this timing parameters, fully distributed FP is the only option that is able to guarantee the shortest HARQ RTT. Between these two cases, the mMTC slice presents an average timing parameters separation of approximately 7 slots, which allows a setup compliant with the edge part of the network.

C. Hierarchical scheduler: slice optimization and user priority performance

In the previous subsection, the optimal timing parameters have been defined for each slice, so as to accomplish the latency requirements. Nevertheless, the system might still be affected by traffic congestion since no spectrum sharing policies are applied. For each slice of $S_n \in k$, a set of thresholds ($th_{n,1}, th_{n,2}$) are defined (randomly) as follows: i) *eMBB*: $th_{1,1} = 0.4$ and $th_{1,2} = 0.7$, ii) *mMTC*: $th_{2,1} = 0.4$ and $th_{2,2} = 0.7$, and iii) *uRLLC*: $th_{3,1} = 0.4$ and $th_{3,2} = 0.7$. In terms of PRB, this initial slice resource partitioning of the k -th entry is graphically represented in Fig. 1, where each slice-mode is highlighted with a different color. Since the real-

time load (*rt-load*) of slice mMTC exceeds $th_{2,2}$, its mode is *Critical*, and the resource sharing procedure is activated by the SM. After the resource optimization, the final PRB configuration per slice is illustrated in Fig. 2, where the mMTC slice increased its capacity through a proportional reduction of uRLLC slice resources. In the final slice parameterization, each slice *rt-load* belongs to *Support* or *Conservative* modes, assuring system stability and optimal performance.

As a further slice refinement, the *intra-slice* scheduler algorithm described in Subsection II-D is performed to define the optimal queuing priority for each user. For each k row solution, we assign a priority factor $\varphi_{u,n}$ to each UE u of each slice S_n ; the maximization problem returns the set of weights illustrated in Fig. 3, clustered per slice. Each color identifies a slice, where each bar is a UE's weight. Considering the *proportional fair allocation* utility function ($\alpha_q = 1$) for each slice, our method correctly defines a weight for each UE proportional to the data-rate, where the sum of the UEs' weight of the same slice is equal to the slice share percentage obtained after the inter-slice optimization (30% eMBB, 25% mMTC, and 45% uRLLC). Compared to the classical fair weight distribution ($\alpha_q \gg 1$), our proportional allocation overcomes under/over resource provisioning issues per UEs (blue and green areas of Fig. 3), which affects the UE's performance, especially for slices characterized by an irregular traffic trend.

Another metric for evaluating the impact of the utility function under different α_q parameter is illustrated in Fig. 4, where the Jain index is calculated for each slice in order to determine whether the UEs are receiving a fair share of radio resources. As expected, for our case ($\alpha_q = 1$) the Jain index is low due to the proportional distribution of the resources according to each UE load, while fair sharing is achieved for each slice when ($\alpha_q > 7$).

D. Graphical abstraction of Nash Equilibrium Strategy Profile

In Fig. 6, the maximum expected value of the utility function is calculated under different number of UEs connected per slice, given distinct random initial weights values, where each scenario is evaluated multiple times (≈ 1000) in order to increase the accuracy of our solution. Under different slice loads, all the curves converge to an optimal utility function value (global optimum), affirming that an UE can not increase its gain from deviating the current strategy. The number of iterations and processing time to reach the global optimum increases according to the UEs served per slice. This solution presents an intuitive and alternative methodology to proof the existence of a Nash Equilibrium in our model, where the desired outcome is achieved by not deviating from the initial problem constraints.

Fig. 5. Slice-based HARQ parameters definition.

Fig. 6. NESP convergence under different slice loads.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a NS RAN orchestration framework for the optimal RAN network functionalities placement, flexible HARQ design, and dynamic radio resource management. Our results show that specific flexible HARQ timing parameterization per service improves the performance in terms of latency, infrastructure design, and system scalability. Simultaneously, a real-time spectrum sharing technique based on a joint user-slice evaluation of the data rate requirements overcomes saturation and over/under provisioning of radio resources. At intra-slice layer, a novel scheduling scheme based on game theory is designed, capable of optimizing the flow priority according to the single user's load. As a future work, the proposed model will be tested on a mature E2E 5G SA testbed (currently under development), and benchmarked against other optimization techniques (i.e., machine learning, stochastic programming, genetic algorithms, etc.).

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